

Project number: 016.Veni.185.491

Title: From Ownership to Access: The Implications of Streaming Digital Content on Consumers, Sellers, and Artists

Applicant: dr. H. Datta

I would like to express my gratitude to the reviewer and the committee member for their positive evaluation of my research qualities and for recognizing the quality, innovative character and potential academic impact of my proposed research. Below, I respond to the substantive points raised in their assessments.

(1) Research qualities and (updated) publication record

Both the reviewer (evaluation: A+) and the committee member compliment my past performance and my pipeline. I am especially grateful to the reviewer for taking the effort to gather data to assess my performance relative to my peer group. I would like to add that my pioneering work on how online streaming changes music consumption has recently been accepted for publication at *Marketing Science*, a top core journal in my field¹. This study sets the stage for the three projects put forward in my proposal, and has already received significant media coverage in several national Dutch newspapers (e.g., *Algemeen Dagblad*, *Nederlands Dagblad*), on online platforms (e.g., nu.nl) and in magazines (e.g., *Emerge*), and generated new industry contacts (e.g., Spotify's R&D department in New York has been in contact with us after we shared with them our main results). My recent publication not only boosts my performance relative to my peer group, but also underscores my growing expertise on this emerging topic.

(2) Developing a course for PhD students

The reviewer suggests to develop a PhD course to stimulate innovation within the marketing community. I like this idea a lot. In fact, I have recently given workshops to PhD students at Tilburg University and HEC Paris on reproducible science using Git/GitHub. I will take an extra effort to extend this initiative, potentially developing a multi-day workshop for PhD students on the new technologies (e.g., unstructured databases, code management for reproducible science) and modeling techniques (e.g., quasi-experimental methods) I use to conduct my research. While such a workshop could be conducted online, I prefer to first develop and test it in our student network. Once it runs smoothly, developing a version suited for larger audiences (i.e., by means of a MOOC) is certainly viable and effective.

¹ Datta, H., G. Knox and B. Bronnenberg, "Changing Their Tune: How Consumers' Adoption of Online Streaming Affects Music Consumption and Discovery", *Marketing Science*, accepted for publication in March 2017.

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(3) Disseminating knowledge to executives at leading organizations

In my proposed strategy to disseminate knowledge, I point out “executives at leading organizations” as a relevant target group. The reviewer asks for clarification on who the “executives at leading organizations” are. For your convenience, below, you can find a list with several of my current industry contacts across various international firms. Several of them are high up in organizations that play a key role in shaping the online streaming business. Others are part of important industry communities where research findings can be shared.

(4) Spill-overs to other disciplines and industries

The reviewer points out that research on online streaming is not limited to the marketing domain, and I fully agree. For example, my work gets cited in the economics and industrial organization literature². Further, Tilburg University’s Data Science Initiative has brought me in contact with researchers at Tilburg’s Centre for Law, Technology, and Society and their work on online video streaming. Last, my research design and potentially also my findings can be used in other industries (e.g., magazines, books, movies).

Once again, I would like to thank the reviewers and the entire evaluation committee for taking the effort to evaluate my work.

Sample list of relevant industry contacts (in alphabetical order):

- Digital Catapult Consultancy, Twine.fm, and (formerly) Musicmetric (CEO, Jeremy Silver)
- Dutch Collection Society Buma/Stemra and Buma Music meets Tech at Eurosonic Noorderslag (Business Development Manager, Andy Zondervan)
- Dutch Collection Society Sena (Business Development Manager, Guido Hogenbirk; Chief Operating Officer, Hans Moolhuijsen)
- Fast Forward (annual network meeting, Founder and Conference Director, Chris Carey)
- Major Label Sony Music International (Senior Vice President Streaming, Rick Van Schooten)
- Paaspop Academy (annual network meeting)
- Streaming Platform Deezer (Marketing Manager, Hoite Polkamp)
- Streaming Platform Spotify (Director of Economics, Will Page; Manager of Research, Manish Nag)

² Belleflame, P. (2016), “The Economics of Digital Goods: A Progress Report,” *Review of Economic Research on Copyright Issues*, 13(2), pp. 1-24; Carroni, E. and D. Paolini (2017), “Content Acquisition by Streaming Platforms: Premium vs Freemium,” Working paper (February 2017).

Application

Grant

Title

From Ownership to Access: The Implications of Streaming Digital Content on Consumers, Sellers, and Artists

Applicant

Dr. H. Datta

Your rebuttal on the referee reports is in progress

Referee report of referee 1

Assessment of the quality of the researcher.

Explanation

Criteria - Quality of the researcher - in terms of profile fit in the target group; - from an international perspective belongs to the 10 to 20% of his/her peer group; - academic excellence as demonstrated by the PhD thesis, publications and/or other relevant achievements in the field; - inspiring enthusiasm for research and/or technology; - persuasiveness; - clear indications of an outstanding talent for academic research. The Veni scheme aims at outstanding researchers only: the top 10-20% of his/her international peer group.

Question a

a

What is your opinion on the past performance of the researcher (as demonstrated by his/her doctoral thesis, publications, and other relevant scientific achievements)?

Comments

Dr. Datta is a very young and ambitious researcher at one of the top schools for marketing research in Europe. In his doctoral thesis, he demonstrated that he works on timely, innovative, and impactful topics, which can make their way into the top journals of our field (Journal of Marketing Research and Journal of Marketing). One of the proposed projects is in the third round at Marketing Science, which I consider the top journal for quantitative marketing research. In addition, he works with excellent researchers in his field (apart from having an outstanding research environment at Tilburg) and is eager to learn from them, specifically in terms of modeling. I have rarely seen a researcher who embraces new technologies and modeling techniques as much as Dr. Datta does.

Question b

b

Does the applicant belong to the top 10-20% of his/her international peer group? Which scientific achievements or talents of the applicant show he/she belongs to this top?

Comments

Yes, absolutely. Dr. Datta started his PhD in 2010 and already published two articles in A-journals. In addition, he has one other project on its way to being published (I know the project and am confident that it will make it into Marketing Science). You can easily compare his performance to colleagues at the leading US schools who started their PhD in 2011 here: <http://www.perceptionstudies.com/docsig2011/index.php>.

If you only consider quantitative marketing students (publishing in Journal of Marketing, Journal of Marketing Research, Management Science, Marketing Science, Quantitative Marketing and Economics), you will notice that there are
- four “students” (Liye Ma, Bryan Bollinger, Masakazu Ishihara, Willy Bolander) with 4-5 A-journal publications,
- three “students” with three A-journal publications (Bart de Langhe, Keisha Cutright, Meng Zhu), and
- 11 “students” with two A-journal publications
between 2011-2016 (the list contains 103 “students”).

Thus, I would clearly say that Dr. Datta belongs to the top 10-20% of his international peer group.

Assessment of the quality, innovative character and academic impact of the proposal

Explanation

Criteria - Quality, innovative character and academic impact of the proposed research - challenging in terms of content; - originality of the research topic; - innovative scientific elements; - potential to make an important contribution to science; - effective in terms of proposed methodology.

Question a

a

Please comment on the relevance of the problem and on the originality and challenging content of the proposal.

Comments

Dr. Datta does research in a field that is very novel and innovative. Streaming services have only emerged in the last 10 years and research in that field is scarce. Thus, we still do not have a good understanding of how these services have affected the entertainment industry: Specifically, we know little about (1) how consumers’ media consumption behavior (demand side) has changed (or is still changing) due to streaming and (2) how artists and content creators (supply side) react to new incentives posed by these income sources. Consequently, Dr. Datta conducts important and potentially impactful research in a very new and innovative field. Since millennials almost exclusively consume media via streaming, his research will even be more important in the future, as traditional ways of media consumption might disappear.

Question b

b

What are the innovative aspects of the proposal? Will the research break new ground by generating new concepts, a deeper understanding, new methods, etc.?

Comments

Yes, I am sure that Dr. Datta’s research will break new ground by generating a deeper understanding of consumers’ media consumption behavior (see above). In addition, Dr. Datta brings rather new methods from information systems and computer science into our field that will help tackle unstructured data and make use of it. Since he also aims to make his code and parts of the data publicly available, I am confident that he will influence the field in a way that these rather new methods are being implemented more and more in the future.

Question c

c

What is your opinion on its potential to make a major contribution to the advancement of scholarship, science or technology (academic impact)?

Comments

As stated above, research in the area of streaming services is scarce and we know very little about how it has affected consumer behavior in the last 10 years. All of the projects that Dr. Datta proposes are novel and will move the field forward in our understanding of how media consumption and content creation changes and might still change within the next years

(specifically, because the new generation merely consumes content via streaming).

His research also has important implications for regulators, as consumption of local content might either get more or less important. As he points out in his proposal, effects could go in both directions, i.e., streaming could lead to defragmentation of tastes and more consumption of local content or it could go into the exact opposite direction, where mostly global content is consumed in the end. The answer can only be provided by conducting empirical research, which is why I am confident that Dr. Datta's research will make a significant contribution to the field.

Question d

d

To what extent is the proposed method effective? Please comment.

Comments

Dr. Datta has invested a lot of time to train himself in state-of-the-art methods, some of which have been developed in other fields (e.g., information systems, computer science) and are rarely being applied in marketing research yet. I consider Dr. Datta to be an expert in methods and believe that the proposed methods are suitable to address potential selection and endogeneity concerns that are very often raised in our field.

Assessment of the knowledge utilisation

Explanation

Criteria - Knowledge utilisation (= KU) NWO uses a broad definition of KU: not only innovative end of pipe product creation is considered, but also purposeful interaction with (potential) knowledge users, such as industry or public organisations and knowledge transfer to other scientific disciplines. NWO asks applicants to fill out the paragraph on KU. An applicant may however explain that KU cannot be expected given the nature of the research project. In that case, we still kindly ask you to assess whether the applicant has provided reasonable argument or evidence sufficiently. Potential - contribution to society and/or other academic areas; - disciplines and organisations that might benefit from the results. Implementation - action plan to allow the outcomes of the research project to benefit the potential knowledge users; - if and how the potential knowledge users will be involved; - (concrete) outcomes for society; - the period over which KU is expected to occur.

Question a

a

What is your opinion on the described relevance of the results of the research?

Comments

I agree with Mr. Datta in that his research will be of interest to a variety of disciplines and not only marketing. Some of the research on streaming services is being conducted in economics and industrial organization, such that his impact is not only limited to marketing. What is even more important is that he plans to make code and data publicly available such that a new generation of PhD students is able to learn from him.

In terms of managerial impact, his work will provide a better understanding of consumer and artist behavior in the music industry, both of which allow music streaming platforms to better serve consumers' tastes and additionally, provide the right incentives for artists to produce content that serves these needs. Furthermore, I strongly believe that his findings will be applicable to other entertainment industries (e.g., books and magazines) that might see similar changes like the music industry.

Finally, regulators will get a better understanding of whether regulation is indeed needed (e.g., whether there needs to be a minimum quota for local content).

Question b

b

Please comment on the effectiveness and feasibility of the proposed approach for knowledge utilisation.

Comments

Dr. Datta proposes four ways of implementing knowledge utilization: (1) involving executives at leading companies, (2) presenting findings to an industry audience, (3) disseminating knowledge via various media outlets and creating sketch board videos, and (4) developing teaching material. All of this seems reasonable and implementable to me.

However, I also urge Dr. Datta to not only prepare teaching material, but also develop a course for PhD students, in which he shares his knowledge such that more students will work in this field in the future. In addition, creating a MOOC might also be a nice way of utilizing generated knowledge and would allow exposure of his ideas to academics as well as practitioners. I am confident that there is demand for such a MOOC that makes new knowledge accessible to a large audience.

Question c

c

Only answer this question in case the applicant argued that knowledge utilisation is not to be expected given the nature of the research proposal: Does the applicant convincingly explain why knowledge utilisation is not applicable for his/her research project (see also the information under criterion 3 listed above)?

Comments

n.a.

Final assessment

Question a

a

How do you assess the entire application?
Please give your final scoring (A+/A/B/UF/U).

Comments referee

01, A+ Highest quality, significance and recommendation for funding

Question b

b

Could you please summarize (point by point) the strengths and weaknesses of the grant application focussing on the candidate, proposal and knowledge utilisation?

Comments

To summarize, Dr. Datta is an excellent researcher in our field who works on novel and innovative projects, which will further our knowledge about how streaming affects consumers' media consumption and artists' content creation. He works in an environment that will clearly allow him to pursue his goals by providing regular feedback and having senior co-authors from leading institutions around the world. His intentions to publish code and data are extremely important to disseminate his knowledge and allow a new generation of PhD students to work in this very important field. Finally, various parties will benefit from his work (businesses, science, and regulators), such that I do not have doubts about the potential impact of his work.

Feedback datamanagement

Explanation

With the data management section NWO mainly wants to raise awareness about the importance of responsible data management. The section is therefore not included in a committee's decision about whether a proposal should be awarded funding or not. NWO does, however, submit this section to the committee and referees for any advice or feedback. After a proposal has been awarded funding the researcher should elaborate the section into a data management plan. For this, applicants can make use of the advice they have received.

Overall

Overall rebuttal

Maximum number of words for the reaction on all referee reports 1300

Waive rebuttal false

Assessment form Veni Social Sciences & Humanities 2017

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1. Quality of the researcher

This concerns the quality of the researcher, assessed on the following criteria:

- In terms of profile fit in the target group;
- in the top 10 to 20% of his/her international peer group;
- academic excellence as demonstrated by the PhD thesis, publications and/or other relevant achievements in the field;
- inspiring enthusiasm for research and/or technology;
- persuasiveness;
- clear indications of an outstanding talent for academic research.

This researcher obtained his PhD in 2013 and has published in two of the top ranking journals in his domain. Other work is under way, but we are asked not to take these into consideration as they are not accepted or published yet.

The researcher has a growing international network, participation in seminars, workshops and conferences including some events related to music festivals. A teaching award was won and he is informally involved in several PhD projects.

2. Quality, innovative character and academic impact of the proposed research

This concerns the quality of the proposal, assessed on the following criteria:

- Challenging content;
- originality of the topic;
- innovative elements;
- potential to make an important contribution to the advancement of science;
- effectiveness of proposed methodology

This project addresses a timely topic, examining online streaming of content to unravel the implications of the shift from ownership to access. In 3 projects, the researcher aims to examine how these developments lead to changes in consumer behavior: 1) does online streaming homogenize or fragment taste; 2) impact on consumption of local vs. global content, and 3) supply-side effects of online streaming. Together, these three studies help in getting an insight in how the supply of new music develops during the rise of streaming and how taste may get harmonized or fragmented (both in terms of type of music and origin of music). This teaches us something about how markets may develop when the transition from ownership to access becomes more prevalent. The methodology seems to be appropriate to address the questions raised - the data can be gathered and ideas on data analysis are well-developed. The proposal is well grounded in the literature.

3. Knowledge utilisation

This concerns the quality of the potential for knowledge utilisation of the research results, assessed on the following criteria:

Potential

- Contribution to society and/or other academic areas;
- disciplines and organisations that might benefit from the results.

Implementation

- Action plan to allow the outcomes of the research project to benefit the potential knowledge users;
- if and how the potential knowledge users will be involved;
- (concrete) outcomes for society and/or other academic disciplines;
- the period over which knowledge utilisation is expected to occur.

The selection committee assesses:

- whether the applicant has given a realistic description of the potential for knowledge utilization;
- and to what extent the applicant has presented a concrete and convincing plan for the implementation of the available potential.

If a researcher is of the opinion that the proposed research is not appropriate for knowledge utilisation then he/she should explain why he/she thinks that knowledge utilisation is not applicable. The selection committee will assess the arguments given for this.

The plans for knowledge dissemination are clearly formulated. Different audiences have been identified and different ways to address these are listed. A relevant audience includes students; the term 'executives at leading organizations' remains a bit vague though. Still, it is clear to see how this research could lead to insights that can also inform other online streaming platforms. Good to see that the algorithms will be made available through open source code repositories.